

Estimation of coverage and energy in bio inspired wireless sensors using Harris hawk algorithm

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ABSTRACT

Wireless sensor networks have various sensors which are wide spread and also equipped with supplies. For the deployment sensor nodes are used for capturing the information, the region of interest is selected and the nodes are deployed. Lower sensing power degrades the DC supply reducing the life of wireless sensor networks, this can also be due to improper sensor deployment. Based on the above various wireless sensor network algorithms are available to compute and implement the required optimal figures. Harris hawk is among the one such algorithm used in wireless sensors. It works on the principle of the bird Harris hawk which catches the prey from a very high altitude, resemblance to this and many other features it is implemented in wireless sensors. Various wireless sensor characteristics can be found, figured and tabulated which are essential in this domain. The characteristics like coverage, connectivity, location, energy, and can be estimated. In the work the coverage and energy fitness is estimated using Harris hawk algorithm and its results are being illustrated.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Exchange of information is a necessity in communication as fast progress in microelectronics is in boom meeting the requirements. This development has led to the drastic involvement of wireless sensor networks. The exchange of information between channels via electromagnetic waves with the help of sensor nodal deployment. This type of connections is wireless capable of travelling long distances with greater potential [1]. The sensors in wireless networks are capable of capturing the information around and passing it to the central station from where it is distributed to the network. The sensors deployed are very small in size which require very low hardware such as supply, processor, actuator, and memory. The coverage and energy parameter are not easily estimated in wireless sensor networks using bio inspired techniques. Harris hawk algorithm [2] is used for finding the optimum location of sensors so as to achieve maximum coverage and energy with awareness to the proper sensor deployment in the optimum area of interest.

2. RELATED WORK

Many wireless sensor networks are also available for optimization like whale algorithm, and particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithm. Several parameters which are essential for sensor network optimization can be estimated using these algorithms [3]-[7]. These algorithms have been used since a period for the

development of wireless sensor networks, Harris hawk is also expected to produce realistic results as other algorithms are capable of doing, but implementation of it in bio inspired algorithms makes it a suitable and new approached mathematical and statistical model for obtaining various parameters [8], [9] which include coverage, energy, and connectivity [10]. The existing used algorithms [11]-[15], some as mentioned above are the basement to the implementation of Harris hawk algorithm and estimation of various essential parameters [16]-[19] using Harris hawk algorithm.

3. METHOD

This algorithm is a metaheuristic algorithm [20], [21] which works on swarm intelligence approach [22]-[24]. Harris hawk algorithm copies the hunting nature of the bird Harris hawk. These Harris hawk birds hunt in group with good coordination amongst them for their prey. Harris hawk birds are very intelligent and a socialist type in nature. These predator birds has evolved two types of phases in Harris hawk i.e. the exploration and exploitation phases.

Harris hawk's perching behaviour in exploration phase is mathematically given as (1).

$$x(t+1) = x_{random}(t) - ra_1 |x_{random}(t) - 2ra_2 x(t)| \quad (1)$$

And the its perching behaviour in exploitation phase is mathematically given as (2),

$$x(t+1) = x_{prey}(t) - x_m(t) - ra_3 (lb + ra_4 (ub - lb)) \quad (2)$$

where,

$x(t+1)$ is hawk's position vector in coming iteration

$x_{prey}(t)$ is prey's position

$x(t)$ is hawk's present position

ra_1 to ra_4 are random numbers in [0,1]

lb is the lower bound

ub is the upper bound

$x_{random}(t)$ is a hawk which is randomly chosen from the present vector.

The estimation of energy is mathematically calculated as (3),

$$E = 2E_0 \left(1 - \frac{t}{T}\right) \quad (3)$$

where:

T is the iteration number

E_0 is the initial energy

With consideration to the above equation,

if $-1 \leq E_0 \leq 0$ then the solution is weak

if $0 \leq E_0 \leq 1$ then the solution is strong

the above equations helps in obtaining the coverage and energy.

3.1. Flow chart of Harris hawk algorithm

The initialization of the algorithm is started with detection and tracking of the sensor data i.e. prey, their initial positions and coming positions are also iterated. The fitness values [25]-[28] are obtained via estimation. When the coverage is obtained, their values are plotted and tabulated. After the obtainment of coverage fitness, energy fitness [29], [30] is obtained and their values are plotted and tabulated. This can be seen in Figure 1. The coverage and energy fitness parameters are obtained by selecting the required inputs, selection of the appropriate phase when required and finally obtaining the required result as shown in Figure 2 using appropriate looping function sets.

Figure 1. Implementation of Harris hawk algorithm

Figure 2. Flow for coverage and energy estimation using Harris hawk algorithm

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Engaging in routine physical activity as a method for maintaining and enhancing one's current level of health is an important goal for many people. A tabular version of these findings can be found in Table 1, and the plotted representations of the values obtained for the five different sets of looping functions can be seen in Figures 3-12. Calculating coverage and energy fitness requires using a loop that iterates through the same collection of functions five times. It has been noticed that once the fitness of the coverage has been computed, it is possible to determine the value of the work that has been invested.

Table 1. Coverage and energy fitness values for five function sets

Parameter	HHO	Value
Function set 1	Coverage	-3.8564
	Energy	-3.8605
Function set 2	Coverage	-3.8529
	Energy	-3.8529
Function set 3	Coverage	-3.8603
	Energy	-3.8529
Function set 4	Coverage	-3.8574
	Energy	-3.8574
Function set 5	Coverage	-2.8431
	Energy	-3.8628

Figure 3. Coverage fitness of function set 1

Figure 4. Energy fitness of function set 1

Figure 5. Coverage fitness of function set 2

Figure 6. Energy fitness of function set 2

Figure 7. Coverage fitness of function set 3

Figure 8. Energy fitness of function set 3

Figure 9. Coverage fitness of function set 4

Figure 10. Energy fitness of function set 4

Figure 11. Coverage fitness of function set 5

Figure 12. Energy fitness of function set 5

5. CONCLUSION

Implementation of Harris hawk algorithm is done and their coverage and energy fitness is estimated. From the observed results it is observed that coverage fitness and energy fitness are directly proportional to each other. It is also observed that energy fitness is dependent on coverage fitness but it is not vice versa, as it is necessary to obtain coverage to obtain energy and the coverage is a set a values whereas the energy is a value obtained as observed from this paper work.

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